

MEDICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF AN ANTIOXIDANT DRUG FOR THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS

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Abstract

One of the pathogenetic mechanisms for the development of periodontal tissue lesions is a violation of lipid peroxidation, antioxidant and metabolic processes. Therefore, it is important to find out the effectiveness of using the antioxidant drug “Ubiquinone” for the treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis. Purpose: to determine the effectiveness of the use of Ubiquinone in the complex treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis.

Material and research methods. . The drug Ubiquinone (Hell) was used to treat 17 patients in the main group; in the second comparison group of 15 patients, periodontal pockets were applied with Metrogyl Denta ointment. To quantitatively assess the condition of periodontal tissues, we used the Schiller-Pisarev test [12], the Fedorov-Volodkina hygiene index [15], the PMA index according to S. Parma [17], and the periodontal index according to A.L. Russell [18].

Keywords: *generalized periodontitis, treatment, Ubiquinone*

The problem of periodontal diseases remains leading in modern dentistry. This is due to their significant prevalence among the population of different age groups and in some places the insufficient effectiveness of healing [4, 5, 10,11]. A feature of periodontal diseases is the reaction of structural formations in the form of a nonspecific dystrophic inflammatory process in response to changes in various body systems [7, 8, 10-13]. One of the pathogenetic mechanisms for the development of periodontal tissue lesions is a violation of lipid peroxidation, antioxidant and metabolic processes [1, 6, 16]. These changes should be taken into account during complex treatment of generalized periodontitis. Based on the above, it is advisable to use antioxidant drugs in the complex treatment of periodontal diseases, in particular the choice of medications, taking into account their therapeutic properties and the pathological links of this periodontal disease [2, 3,7, 8, 10. 11]. In particular, our attention was drawn to the new drug “Ubiquinone” (Hell, Germany). Ubiquinone is prescribed to stimulate defense mechanisms, neutralize the effects of toxins. It normalizes impaired body functions, restores blocked enzyme systems and acts on degenerative diseases (cellular phase). The pharmacodynamics of this medical drug consists of activating and regulating the enzyme systems of the body. It improves cellular respiration processes, has anti-inflammatory, metabolic, immunocorrective effects, antioxidant properties, activates the body's defenses and normalizes impaired functions. Ubiquinone is partly included in the

composition of the drug with antioxidant effect “Coenzyme Q10”. Available in ampoules of 2.2 ml for injection, approved by the Ministry of Health of Ukraine on May 13, 2013 No. 367–No./0018/01/01, amended on July 7, 2016 No. 685. The goal is to determine the effectiveness of the use of Ubiquinone in the complex treatment of patients with general periodontitis .

Material and research methods

During the study, 32 patients with generalized periodontitis of the I-II degree of chronic course were examined [4]. A comprehensive clinical examination of the condition of periodontal tissues was carried out in all patients. To quantitatively assess the condition of periodontal tissues, we used the Schiller-Pisarev test [12], the Fedorov-Volodkina hygiene index [15], the PMA index according to S. Parma [17], and the periodontal index according to A.L. Russel [18], resistance of periodontal vessels V.I. Kulazhenko [5, 6, 9]. For drug treatment of patients in the main group after careful removal of periodontal irritating factors, the drug “Ubiquinone” (Hell, Germany) was used. It was injected into periodontal pockets and the drug was applied to the gums. To enhance the overall effect of the drug on the disturbed parts of the metabolism of patients, Ubiquinone injections of 1.0 ml were administered under the mucous membrane of the transitional fold, in the affected areas (after the test) once every two days. The course of treatment lasted 10–12 days. In the second comparison group, after removing dental deposits and irritants, the periodontal pockets were washed with a solution of hydrogen peroxide and Metrogil

Denta ointment was applied to the clear and injected into the periodontal pockets. using a treatment method using Ubiquinone in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis, bleeding, a feeling of heaviness, itching and soreness in the gums decreased after 1–2 visits. After 3 sessions of treatment of patients with the first degree of chronic course, the phenomena of inflammation in the gums almost completely disappeared in all examined patients. The gum mucosa was dense, acquired a pale pink color, swelling and hyperemia were absent. Periodontal pockets The depth of periodontal pockets was significantly reduced. At the first stage of the disease, the release of exudate from periodontal pockets stopped and their depth decreased to 0.5-0.8 mm. Epithelization of the bottom of periodontal pockets was observed. The pathological mobility of teeth was significantly reduced. osteoporosis of the alveolar bone. In cases of I–II degrees of chronic generalized periodontitis, already after the 3rd treatment session, a cessation or reduction in bleeding and hyperemia of the gum mucosa was observed. The unpleasant (subjective sensations) in the gums stopped. The phenomena of discharge from periodontal pockets decreased or completely disappeared. A decrease in their depth to 0.8–1.0 mm was observed. On radiographs, a decrease in the phenomena of osteoporotic tissue of the alveolar growth of the jaws was also observed. In patients with generalized periodontitis of the second group, after a course of drug treatment, bleeding and pain in the gums also stopped, and the depth of discharge from periodontal pockets decreased. But for this purpose in this group of patients the number of visits was significantly greater. For grade I chronic generalized periodontitis, the number of visits averaged up to 7, and for grades I–II – up to 9. The effectiveness of our treatment results is evidenced by data from an index assessment of periodontal condition and functional tests. After a course of treatment using Ubiquinone, the condition of the periodontal tissues gradually recovered. Thus, the level of inflammation in the gums decreased, as evidenced by a change in the PMA index from 56.4 ± 2.5 to $26.8 \pm 1.9\%$ after treatment. The resistance of periodontal vessels increased (vacuum hematoma according to V.I. Kulazhenko) from 2.90 to 18.0 seconds. The periodontal index remained virtually unchanged, suggesting more distant observations. The depth of periodontal pockets decreased from 2.6 ± 3.5 to 1.3 ± 0.3 . In patients with generalized periodontitis in the comparison group, the clinical picture also changed in a positive direction, but the courses of treatment were more protracted and changes in indices were less effective. The index (PMA) when assessing gum inflammation changed from 56.4 ± 2.5 to $32.5 \pm 2.0\%$, PI remained unchanged. Vascular resistance increased from 2.9 to 14 seconds. Thus, the data obtained indicate the effective effect of Ubiquinone on periodontal tissues of patients with generalized periodontitis. In the immediate term of treatment, a significant change in clinical parameters is observed, which in turn characterizes dystrophic-inflammatory processes in the periodontium. periodontitis. Taking into account the dynamics of positive changes, which is characterized by a reduction in the number of visits to the doctor, it can be argued that the use of this

method of treating patients with generalized periodontitis is more clearly effective in the short term of observation.

Conclusions.

Results.

The use of Ubiquinone in the complex treatment of patients with generalized periodontitis makes it possible to achieve an improvement in the condition of periodontal tissues in the short term of treatment. The positive effect of treatment is confirmed by the positive dynamics of clinical indicators and periodontal indices.

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